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ABOUT THE "MICROCRACK-FLUID" EFFECT DURING LIQUID MOVEMENT IN MICROCRACKED CHANNELS MAMMADOVA

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Abstract

There are numerous investigations of the fluids flow in the small-sized channels in the reference. It is shown that the experimental results of hydraulic resistances in these channels are more than the estimated ones according to theoretical formulas. There are given supposed different explanations without quantitative estimation. The numerous experimental results in the reliable setting are given in this work.

Firstly, the experimental-estimated methodology for "microcrack-fluid" system has been proposed and realized for the quantitative estimation of the hydraulic resistances. This approach allows to conduct hydrodynamic engineering evaluations for fluid flow in the cracked-porous medium, for lubrication in the systems of mechanical engineering, instrument engineering and also for solutions of the sealing problems in different branches of industry and medicine.

Keywords: opening, hydraulic resistance, anomalous oil, "microcrack- fluid" effect

1. Introduction

Presently the mechanical properties of fluids are investigated in pipes of various sizes. The investigations are shown that the resistance of the fluid flow is increased in comparison with the estimated formulas in the small-sized pipes. This phenomenon can be explained with different qualitative factors.

Currently the considerable factual material according to research of non-Newtonian fluids flow in the cracks has been accumulated. Numerous experimental and theoretical investigations have been conducted [1-4 and etc.]. But there is no consensus about the manifestation of the anomalous behavior of Newtonian fluids and strengthening the rheological properties of non-Newtonian systems in the microcracks. Taking into consideration this situation in the fluid mechanics we have carried out the experiments in specially developed unit with different fluids: water, viscous and anomalous oils [5, 6].

2. The experimental unit and research results.

The methodology of determining the parameters of channel porous systems, namely: the values of the crack opening, medium flow coefficient and fluid rheology in the complicated conditions. The experimental investigations have been conducted on the units allowing create plane-parallel and plane-radial cracks of the different opening - h . Overlooking plane-parallel unit due to simplicity of the description we have described in detail the peculiarities of the plane-radial unit. The cracked model structure simulating plane-radial fluid flow in the nondeformable medium is shown in Fig. 1. The plates with 168 mm diameter pressed between 1 and 7 flanges are roof - 6 and bottom - 2 of the crack. Under the influence of differential pressure the investigated fluid enters through the nozzle 4 into the sleeve 5 pressuring annular cavity by rubber seals 3 and then it enters into the crack between the plates and into the system for measuring fluid flow in the nozzle 8. With the objective of ensuring crack nondeformability the plates are made of 40 X steel which after thermal processing

by high frequency currents have surface hardness of 40-50 Rockwell units.

Fig.1. Plane-radial crack model

The inner plates' surface have been processed and grinded with accuracy corresponding to 10 category. In order to obtain the cracks with the mentioned opening the non-wettable layerings with 5x7 mm dimensions have been used which are located at 120° angle to each other. The layerings' thickness was chosen in dependence on the value of the required crack opening. For crack deformation control there was used indicating gauge fixed on the upper plate of model. Besides holes in the center and in the contour there were also drilled two holes in order to controlling the pressure distribution along the length, i.e. along radius of upper plate. It should be noted that crack length - L is 84 mm. The circles radii are equal to 34 and 57 mm whereon the holes are located relative each other at an angle of 120°. Moreover other holes were located near these holes at distances of 43 mm from the crack center.

The unit was tested for leak proofness at 50 MPa

pressure for all the crack sizes and it was tested crack safety at all points of the upper plate where indicating gauge were fixed. The maximal pressure was less than 2 MPa in the experimental investigations.

Experimental investigations in the plane-radial cracks were carried out in two series: the fluid flow was modeled from plane-radial crack center to its contour - the first series and the second series from crack contour to center. The experiments in both series were carried out at steady-state condition of the fluid flow.

The experiments were carried out under isothermal conditions. All motion ways of the investigated fluid in the model was in termobath. The constant temperature was maintained by ultratermostat provided with contact thermometer installed directly in termobath.

During the experiments the change in thickness of crack was not observed i.e. it was eliminated an opinion about formation of fluid layers on the channel walls.

For exception of different effects the crack saturation was made by the investigated fluid under slight pressure with simultaneous vacuuming.

Different pressure drops were created on cracked model, after achievement of the steady-state filtration regime the appropriate volumetric water discharges $-Q$ were measured. The hydrodynamic peculiarities of the different fluids were investigated according to the obtained data.

3. The results of the experimental investigations, their processing and generalization

The experiments results were processed in the co-

ordinates $\gamma - \tau$, where $\gamma = \frac{Q}{4\pi rh^2}$ - the average velocity gradient and $\tau = \frac{\Delta Ph}{L}$ - tangential shear stress.

During experimental investigations of water, viscous and non-Newtonian oils in microcracks it has been revealed new determining parameter - firstly founded "microcrack-fluid" effect without considering of which it is impossible to carry out different technological processes of oil industry, mechanical engineering, instrument engineering, medicine and etc.

During motion of viscous-one parameter fluid in the channels with opening being less than the critical one - $h < h_{cr}$, viscous fluid becomes anomalous i.e. two-parameter but during motion in channels - $h > h_{cr}$, the one-parameter fluid remains one parameter. For anomalous fluids the rheological properties of the fluid are increased in channels - $h < h_{cr}$ and they remain unchanged in channels - $h > h_{cr}$.

As a result of experimental research of fluid flow in microcrack it has been determined that water behaves like non-Newtonian fluid at the crack opening values below 30 or 35 μm respectively at temperatures of 293 and 303 K. Such properties are defined for water and Newtonian fluids. Such opening is called the critical opening. The critical sizes of crack have been determined for various fluids.

In the case of non-Newtonian oil flow in the plane and plane-radial cracks with increasing opening the limiting yield stress and apparent viscosity of oil are decreased up to certain value of the crack opening. The limiting yield stress and apparent viscosity don't depend on h and remain constant at 180 μm opening values and at 303 K temperature.

Fig. 2 and 3 shows the dependences of the average velocity gradient - γ on tangential shear stress - τ in different values of crack opening quantity during motion of water and anomalous oil in the plane-radial microcracks at 303 K temperature.

As seen from Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 at $h \geq h_{cr}$ for different values of crack opening all points of dependencies - $\gamma = \gamma(\tau)$ respectively for water (4 and 5 lines) and anomalous oil (4-6 lines) are fallen on the straight line for both viscous and anomalous fluids - $\gamma = \gamma(\tau)$. This proves the reliability of the defined critical values of crack opening.

Therefore firstly based on experimental data we have determined critical value of opening - h_{cr} , i.e., it has been found that the changes are practically absent at $h \geq h_{cr}$ in the rheological properties of the fluid. The anomalous properties are manifested at $h < h_{cr}$ during viscous fluids flow in the crack and rheological parameters are increased during anomalous fluids motion and these effects disappear at $h > h_{cr}$.

This developed approach allows to conduct hydrodynamic engineering evaluations for fluid flow in cracked-porous medium, for lubrication in the systems of the mechanical engineering, instrument engineering and also for solutions of the sealing problems in different branches of industry and medicine.

5. Conclusions

On the basis of the experimental investigations and theoretical generalizations of the results about different fluids motion in the cracked channels "there are developed the basics of fluids mechanics in very little permeable media and micro-cracked channels":

1. During fluid motion in the crack with opening - $h \leq h_{cr}$ in the "crack-fluid" system the non-Newtonian properties for the viscous fluid are manifested and rheological properties are increased for anomalous fluid but the mentioned microcracked effects are absent at $h > h_{cr}$;

2. The obtained micro-cracked effect for gas- or air-free homogeneous fluid is as the additional resistance being similar to Jamin effect and it can increase Jamin effect during two and three phase fluids flow in microcracks systems;

3. The determined critical values of crack opening are 35 and 30 μm for water at 293 and 303 K temperatures and they are 130 and 180 μm for viscous and anomalous oil at 303 K respectively.

In fluids hydrodynamics for elimination of the influence of the cracks opening degree, i.e. "crack-fluid" effect it is necessary to have effect on "microcrack-fluid" system by powerful ultrasound, hydrodynamic, acoustic and other waves which requires to make special settings.

Fig. 2. Dependence of γ on τ during water motion in the plane-radial microcracks, at opening values, μm : 10 (curve - 1), 15 (curve - 2), 20 (curve - 3), 30 (straight line - 4) and 35 (straight line - 5), $T = 303 \text{ K}$

Fig. 3. Dependence of γ on τ during non-Newtonian oil motion in the plane-radial microcracks at opening values, μm : 90 (curve - 1), 120 (curve - 2), 160 (curve - 3), 180 (curve - 4), 220 (curve - 5) and 240 (curve - 6), $T = 303 \text{ K}$

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